

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS EXPRESSING HUMAN CHARACTER IN ENGLISH AND UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract:

This article presents the linguistic results of the analysis of phraseological units expressing human character in English and Uzbek. Phraseology is considered as one of the components that make up the figurative, emotional and stylistic wealth of the language. In the process of research, phraseology is studied in semantic, structural and stylistic terms.

Keywords:

phraseology, phraseological unit, human characteristics, linguistic production, comparative analysis, semantics, stylistics.

Introduction

Language serves as an important mirror of human thinking and culture. Each language has the ability to express the inner world, behavior and mental state of a person through its lexical richness, grammatical structure and figurative means of expression. One of the main tools that demonstrate such possibilities of language is phraseological units. Phraseological units give speech imagery, emotionality and expressiveness, help to convey thoughts more effectively. Therefore, phraseological units are studied as a separate scientific direction in linguistics. Although English and Uzbek languages belong to different language families, both languages have phraseological units that express human character. They reflect the national identity of the language and are also of particular importance in the translation process. Therefore, the comparative study of phraseological units in English and Uzbek is one of the important scientific tasks in linguistics.

Phraseology and the concept of phraseological units: Phraseology occupies a strong place in linguistics as a branch of linguistics that studies stable word combinations. Phraseological units are stable combinations in which the words in the composition do not have a separate meaning, but together express a certain transferable meaning. They enrich the lexical and stylistic layer of the language and increase the imagery, emotionality and expressiveness of speech.

Linguist A. V. Kunin defines phraseological units as follows: "Phraseological units are stable combinations of words with partially or fully transferred meanings" [Kunin, 1984: 36-37]. As can be seen from this definition, phraseological units have two main properties: stability and transferability. Stability means that the words of a phraseological unit cannot be changed or their meaning may be lost as a result of the change. The mobile meaning refers to a new semantic value that differs from the individual meaning of the words in the unit. For example, the English phrase to break the ice, when translated literally, means "muzni sindirish", but as a phraseological unit it means "muloqotni boshlash, ilk qadamni qo'yish". In Uzbek, the phrase to "qo'lini uzatmoq" has a similar semantic property and means the beginning of friendly relations between individuals. The linguistic study of phraseological units includes determining their semantic, structural and stylistic features. Semantically, they have a mobile meaning, often formed using metaphor, metonymy or other means of artistic depiction. Structurally, phraseological units can be manifested in various grammatical forms, for example, an adjective + noun combination (cold-hearted person), a verb combination (to lose one's temper) or a

stable expression (a burni baland). Stylistically, they make speech more lively and expressive, and allow you to convey the author's emotional point of view.

Phraseological units are closely related to the culture, historical experience and mentality of the people. Each society expresses its life experience and values through language. Therefore, phraseological units are considered not only linguistic units, but also as a cultural phenomenon. Sh. Rahmatullayev explains the importance of phraseological units as follows: "Phraseological units form the figurative layer of the language, reflecting the lifestyle and worldview of the people" [Rahmatullayev, 1992: 45]. Linguist I. V. Arnold emphasized the evaluative function of phraseological units, stating that "Phraseological units often serve to express the speaker's evaluation of a person or situation" [Arnold, 1986: 52]. This means that phraseological units serve as an important tool in describing a person's character, behavior, and mental state. They make speech short, but clear and figurative. For example, the English expression "heart of gold" expresses a person's generosity and kindness, while the Uzbek expression "ko'ngli keng" expresses the same positive quality. In this way, phraseological units also reflect national characteristics. Another important aspect of phraseology is its close connection with culture. Each people reflects its life experience, values, and traditions through language. Therefore, the study of phraseological units is important not only from the point of view of linguistics, but also from the point of view of ethnolinguistics and cultural studies. If the Uzbek expression "tili zahar" describes a person's bitter or cruel words, then the English expression "sharp-tongued" denotes the same negative quality. This indicates the connection of phraseological units with the culture and mentality of the people. Phraseology includes stable combinations, idioms, proverbs and various expressions. Each of them enriches the figurative layer of the language and expands the emotional and stylistic possibilities of speech. With the help of phraseological units, a person's character is briefly and clearly described, which increases the effectiveness of speech in artistic, scientific and colloquial speech.

Also, phraseological units convey different nuances in speech depending on the context. For example, the English phrase "to carry weight" usually means "og'ir ma'noga ega bo'lmoq", while the phrase carry weight in decision-making in a phraseological context means "qaror qabul qilish jarayonida ta'sirli bo'lmoq". In Uzbek, the phrase "og'ir so'z" gives a similar semantic nuance. This indicates the context-dependent nature of phraseological units.

Phraseological units expressing human character: Expressing human character is one of the most important functions of language. Language serves as the main tool for reflecting a person's inner world, mental state and behavior. Phraseological units are considered one of the most effective tools for describing human character. They allow you to briefly and figuratively express not only positive and negative qualities, but also subtle nuances in human behavior. When analyzing phraseological units semantically, their functions in describing human character are divided into several main groups:

1. Phraseological units expressing positive character qualities:

Expressing positive traits of a person's character is one of the most important functions of language. Language is not only a means of transmitting information, but also serves to describe a person's inner world, mental state and social qualities. In this regard, phraseological units are an effective means of expressing positive character traits in a short, clear and figurative way.

Semantically, phraseological units expressing a positive character indicate a person's inner qualities, behavior in accordance with social norms and attitude towards others. Positive phraseological units also affect a person's social relationships. For example, the English phrase warm-hearted indicates that a person is kind and caring towards others, while the Uzbek phrase "ko'ngli toza" emphasizes the sincerity and openness of a person. These phraseological units serve to describe not only individual, but also social qualities. The stylistic feature of phraseological units is of particular importance in expressing a positive character. They give speech warmth, sincerity and emotional tone. In this regard, phraseological units are a means of vividly and figuratively conveying the positive aspects of human character in fiction, journalism and oral speech. As the linguist V. V. Vinogradov noted, "Phraseological units are one of the most expressive means of language" [Vinogradov, 1977: 88]. This means that phraseological units allow us to clearly and effectively express the positive qualities of human character. Also, positive phraseological units can express different nuances depending on the context. In English, the expression "to have a heart of gold" in ordinary speech indicates a generous and kind person, while in a literary text this expression allows for a more in-depth description of a person's inner world and spiritual affection. In Uzbek, the expression "ko'ngli keng" means the sincerity of a person, and depending on the context, it can also reflect his social and cultural qualities. Phraseological units also reflect national character. In phraseological units expressing a positive character in English, body parts such as heart, soul, mind are widely used as metaphorical means of depiction. In Uzbek, words such as *ʁənyʁ*, *dil*, *ʁpyʁk* reflect national mentality and values. Therefore, phraseological units expressing a positive character are important not only as a linguistic, but also as a cultural phenomenon.

2. Phraseological units expressing negative character qualities:

Expressing negative traits of a person's character is one of the important functions of language. Language serves not only as a means of transmitting information, but also as a means of describing negative aspects of a person's inner world, mental state and behavior. In this regard, phraseological units are an effective means of expressing negative character traits in a short, clear and figurative way. In addition, the research of linguist R. Moon emphasizes the psychological function of phraseological units. He writes: "Idiomatic expressions often encode emotional attitudes and moral judgments, allowing speakers to convey criticism or disapproval efficiently" [Moon, 1998: 67]. In this regard, phraseological units expressing a negative character give speech a critical tone, emotional power and emotional impact.

Semantically, phraseological units expressing negative character traits semantically indicate the internal and external qualities of a person, as well as behavior that is perceived negatively in social and cultural terms. For example, the English phrase two-faced describes a hypocritical person, while the phrase big-headed describes an arrogant person. In Uzbek, phraseological units such as "ikki yuzlamachi, burni baland, and tili zahar" reflect the negative qualities of a person. These phraseological units give tension to speech, and they can be used as a critical function in artistic, journalistic, and official speech. Also, negative phraseological units play an important role in assessing a person's social behavior. For example, the English phrase "backstabber" expresses hypocrisy and betrayal, while the Uzbek phrase "orqadan sanchmoq" indicates the same situation. These phraseological units give a serious tone and critical perspective to speech.

From a stylistic point of view, phraseological units expressing a negative character give the speech tension, drama and emotional tone. In fiction, they are used to clearly and vividly describe the negative qualities of individuals. As the linguist B. Bergen notes in his research, "Idiomatic and figurative language allows speakers and writers to convey subtle emotional nuances, including criticism and disapproval, in a compact and impactful way" [Bergen, 2012: 54]. In this regard, negative phraseological units allow us to briefly, but clearly and figuratively express the negative aspects of a person's character. The context-dependent nature of phraseological units is also important. For example, the English expression "to have a chip on one's shoulder" usually indicates a person's humiliated or offended state, but in a literary text this expression serves to more deeply describe the person's angry and harsh character. In Uzbek, the expression "dili og'ir" (a hard-hearted person) expresses a person's harsh, critical, or harsh character. In this way, phraseological units convey different nuances depending on the context and increase the impact of speech.

In terms of national characteristics, phraseological units are of great importance not only as linguistic units, but also as phenomena reflecting national culture and mentality. The phraseological fund of each language reflects its cultural values, social norms and historical experience. In this regard, phraseological units expressing negative character traits are also an important source in the study of national characteristics. In phraseological units expressing negative character in English, body parts such as heart, tongue, head are widely used as metaphorical means. For example, the expression "cold-hearted" denotes a cold, emotionally insensitive person, the expression "sharp-tongued" denotes a person prone to critical, harsh words, and "big-headed" describes an arrogant and arrogant person. These phraseological units in English allow for a clear and figurative expression of the negative aspects of a person's character and give an emotional tone to speech. In the Uzbek language, national mentality and values are expressed more through metaphorical means such as heart, tongue, and heart. For example, the expression "ko'ngli tor" indicates that a person is devoid of openness and generosity, while "tili zahar" indicates that a person is prone to harsh, harsh and critical words. The expression "burni baland" expresses a person's arrogant, arrogant character. In this way, Uzbek phraseological units serve as a means of reflecting national values, social norms and mentality.

It should also be noted that the national character of phraseological units is manifested in their metaphorical structure, context of use and stylistic tone. For example, if the English expression "to be a snake in the grass" denotes hypocrisy and gossip, then in the Uzbek language there are similar expressions "ikki yuzlamaachi" or "orqadan pichoq sanchmoq", which were formed taking into account national oral culture, historical experience and social values. In this regard, phraseological units expressing negative character traits deserve in-depth study not only as a linguistic, but also as a cultural phenomenon. They are an important means of reflecting the semantic richness of the language, national thinking and mentality, as well as social behavior.

Types of phraseological units: Phraseological units expressing a negative character can be divided into several groups semantically and stylistically:

1. Units expressing hypocrisy: in English "two-faced", "backstabber"; in Uzbek "ikki yuzli", "orqandan sanchmoq".

2. Units expressing arrogance and haughtiness: in English "big-headed", "full of oneself"; in Uzbek "burni baland", "o'zini osmonga tutmoq".
3. Units expressing harsh words and harsh behavior: in English "sharp-tongued", "hard-hearted"; in Uzbek "tili zahar", "ko'ngli tor".
4. Units expressing impatience and anger: in English "short-tempered", "hot-headed"; in Uzbek "jahli tez", "joni qattiq".

These groups demonstrate the semantic and stylistic richness of phraseological units, as well as the possibilities of using them in different contexts of speech.

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